

HCL HPVoice

Digital promotion campaign for HPV
vaccination through co-creation with
beneficiaries

REPORT

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This document has sought to adopt inclusive language that respects gender differences. However, when it was not possible to find a stylistically appropriate neutral formulation, the masculine form has been used, in accordance with traditional Italian linguistic conventions.

Executive Summary

The **Health Community Lab (HCL) – HPVoice** project was created with the aim of promoting vaccination against Human Papilloma Virus (HPV) among adolescents in Tuscany, through an innovative approach of **participatory digital communication**. In a context characterised by online misinformation and vaccine hesitancy, HPVoice directly involved young people as **co-creators of public health messages**, transforming them from passive recipients to active protagonists of change.

Carried out in collaboration with the University of Florence, the University of Pisa and the IMT School for Advanced Studies in Lucca, the project adopted the **HCL** methodology, divided into three phases: preliminary analysis of the context, co-creation of communication content through the **Social Challenge**, and experimental evaluation of the effectiveness of digital strategies through a **Randomised Controlled Trial**. The activities involved over 500 high school students in Tuscany, who designed and tested social media campaigns on Instagram and TikTok dedicated to HPV prevention.

The results showed that peer-based and co-created communication is perceived as more authentic and engaging, improving knowledge about HPV and encouraging informed reflection on vaccination, although the impact on vaccination behaviour is still limited. The experience also strengthened participants' sense of **agency** and trust in health institutions, demonstrating the educational and social value of the HCL approach.

In conclusion, HPVoice represents a **replicable model of social and health innovation**, capable of integrating research, education and digital communication to promote a culture of prevention and shared responsibility. The evidence gathered suggests that the Tuscany Region should consolidate HCL workshops as permanent tools for youth participation, co-creation and health promotion.

Key Messages

- **Co-creation and youth participation:**
Young people are not just recipients, but active protagonists in the construction of health messages. Their voice is essential to make communication more authentic and effective.
- **Digital communication for prevention:**
Social media can become powerful tools for health promotion if used with language and formats that are familiar to adolescents.
- **HPV vaccination as an informed choice:**
The vaccine protects both oneself and others: it is a gesture of responsibility and mutual care.
- **Overcoming bias and misinformation:**
Countering fears, stereotypes and procrastination with accessible, clear and engaging scientific information is essential to strengthening confidence in vaccines.
- **Collaboration between institutions, schools and research:**
Integration between academia, schools and healthcare creates an educational ecosystem that promotes empowerment and civic participation.

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1. Introduction

The HPVoice project was created with the aim of promoting vaccination against Human Papilloma Virus (HPV) among adolescents in Tuscany, through an innovative approach to digital communication and active participation. In a context where online misinformation and vaccine hesitancy still represent significant obstacles to prevention, HPVoice aims to transform young people from mere recipients to co-creators of the public health message.

The initiative, carried out thanks to the collaboration between the University of Florence, the University of Pisa and the IMT School for Advanced Studies in Lucca, adopts the *Health Community Lab* (HCL) methodology to involve secondary school students in a shared design process. Through laboratories, workshops and social challenge activities, participants contributed to the creation of communication content for a social media campaign capable of speaking the language of their peers and overcoming the main cognitive biases related to risk perception and vaccination decisions.

HPVoice is therefore a model of social and digital innovation applied to public health: a project that combines research, education and creativity to promote a more aware, responsible and informed health citizenship. The co-creative approach adopted not only makes communication campaigns more effective, but also promotes a cultural change in the way institutions dialogue with the younger generations.

The Tuscany Health Ecosystem and the Health Community Lab

The *Tuscany Health Ecosystem (THE)* is a research project promoted **by the Tuscany Region and all Tuscan universities**, including the University of Florence, funded by the MUR (Ministry of University and Research) through the National Recovery and Resilience Plan (PNRR funded by the European Union - Next Generation EU, Mission 4, Component 2, CUP B83C22003920001). THE has been **divided into 10 macro research themes**, assigned to the spokes, all related to life sciences issues. In particular, spoke 10 has been named 'Population Health'. The universities and public and private bodies participating in spoke 10 (Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna, University of Florence, University of Pisa, University of Siena, University for Foreigners of Siena, Dedalus spa) aimed to **integrate methods and tools to improve the ability to implement the innovations that will be introduced in the coming years in our health service**, especially through the involvement of the population and the community.

The Department of Economics and Management (DISEI), together with the Department of Architecture (DIDA), the Department of Education, Languages, Intercultural Studies, Literature and Psychology (FORLILPSI), and the Department of Health Sciences (DSS), have conducted research in the field of '*Community engagement and social innovation for health and well-being of individuals and territories*', developing the **Health Community Lab (HCL)** methodology, i.e. a collaborative space involving citizens, institutions, businesses and universities to **co-create innovative solutions dedicated to the health and well-being of a community or territory**. As part of the project, each HCL developed tested the methodology in different contexts (for further information, see Biggeri et al. 2025a and Biggeri et al. 2025b), specifically testing certain parts of the process. The HCLs thus made it possible to **verify and refine the methodology**

through concrete cases, even though these were **partial applications**, limited to specific areas, problems or topics of intervention.

2. Theoretical and epidemiological background

2.1 Epidemiology and description of HPV infection

Human papillomavirus (HPV) infection is one of the most common sexually transmitted infections globally and is a public health problem of worldwide significance. The World Health Organisation estimates that approximately 80% of sexually active people will contract HPV at least once in their lifetime (WHO, 2020). In 2022, more than 660,000 new cases of HPV-related cancers were reported globally, of which approximately 95% were cervical cancers (Casigliani et al., 2024).

HPV is a DNA virus belonging to the *Papillomaviridae* family, with more than 200 identified genotypes, at least 13 of which are classified as high-risk oncogenic. The HPV-16 and HPV-18 genotypes are responsible for approximately 70% of cervical cancer cases and a large proportion of cancers of the anus, oropharynx, vagina and penis (WHO, 2025). The infection is mainly transmitted sexually, and most infections are transient and asymptomatic: in 70–90% of cases, the virus is spontaneously eliminated within two years. However, in persistent forms of oncogenic strains, progression to precancerous lesions and, over time, to invasive cancer may occur (ISS, 2022).

Within Europe, the incidence of cervical cancer varies considerably: Italy has one of the lowest rates (approximately 2,365 new cases in 2020), but the burden of disease remains significant, with approximately 1,500 deaths per year (Ministry of Health, 2025). The infection particularly affects adolescents and young adults, who represent the age group most exposed to new infections due to the onset of sexual activity and the higher frequency of partners. This makes primary prevention through vaccination a strategic priority in protecting young people's health.

2.2 Vaccination and cancer screening in Italy

HPV vaccination is the most effective preventive measure against oncogenic forms of the virus. Introduced in Italy in 2007 for 12-year-old girls, it was subsequently extended to boys of the same age, in line with European recommendations for gender-neutral vaccination (ECDC, 2021). Currently, the 9-valent vaccine is the only one used in the national programme, offering coverage against the nine genotypes responsible for approximately 90% of HPV-related cancers (ISS, 2022).

The 2023–2025 National Vaccination Prevention Plan (PNPV) provides for active and free vaccination for 11–12-year-old boys and girls, with the possibility of free catch-up vaccination in subsequent cohorts (Ministry of Health, 2023). However, vaccination coverage remains below the 95% target set by the WHO for the elimination of cervical cancer by 2030. In 2022, in Italy, coverage for the first dose among 12-year-olds was 55% for girls and 47% for boys, with wide regional differences (Ministry of Health, 2023).

The Tuscany Region stands out for its inclusive policies, offering the vaccine free of charge to individuals up to the age of 18 and to at-risk groups, such as men who have sex with men and immunocompromised individuals (Tuscany Region, 2022). However, even in Tuscany, vaccination uptake among young people remains below the desired targets, highlighting the need for new communication strategies (Menicagli et al., 2024).

In addition to vaccination, Italy has regionally organised cervical screening programmes, which include Pap tests every three years for women aged 25 to 29 and HPV-DNA tests every five years for women aged 30 to 64 (ISS, 2022). These programmes, when combined with vaccination, have been shown to significantly reduce the incidence and mortality of cervical cancer. However, the elimination target set by the WHO — 90% vaccination coverage, 70% screening and 90% access to treatment — requires an unprecedented communication and organisational effort, with a particular focus on young people as a priority target (WHO, 2025).

2.3 Vaccine hesitancy and cognitive biases

Despite the proven effectiveness of HPV vaccines, *vaccine hesitancy* remains a significant barrier to their uptake. According to the WHO, this is defined as 'reluctance or refusal to be vaccinated despite the availability of services' (WHO, 2020). The causes of hesitancy are multifactorial and include cognitive, emotional, social and cultural aspects.

Among young people and their parents, the main determinants are low risk perception, *information avoidance*, distrust of institutions and the influence of online misinformation. In many cases, HPV is perceived as a distant risk, associated exclusively with adulthood or 'promiscuous' sexual behaviour, which reduces the perceived urgency of vaccination (Casigliani et al., 2024).

Numerous studies, including the HPVoice trial, have shown that the decision to vaccinate is influenced by specific cognitive biases, i.e. mental shortcuts that lead to systematic deviations from rational reasoning (Casigliani et al., 2022).

- **Present bias:** leads to favouring immediate benefits over future ones. Adolescents and their parents tend to underestimate the long-term benefits of vaccination compared to the momentary discomfort of the injection or the fear of side effects.
- **Omission bias:** leads to considering 'acting' (vaccinating) more risky than 'not acting' (not vaccinating), overestimating rare adverse events and underestimating the real risk of infection.
- **Information avoidance:** leads to actively avoiding information that may cause anxiety or guilt, such as the link between HPV and sexual behaviour.
- **Confirmation bias:** leads people to seek only information that is consistent with their initial beliefs, reinforcing doubts and fears, often fuelled by content on social networks.
- **Framing effect:** this affects how messages are perceived based on the tone (positive or negative) in which they are formulated; communication focused on benefits ('protect yourself and your loved ones') is more effective than communication based on threats or blame.

In the case of HPV, hesitation is further complicated by **the stigma** associated with the sexually transmitted nature of the infection: many parents fear that vaccinating their children may be interpreted as encouraging early sexual activity. However, the scientific literature clearly refutes this perception: vaccination does not affect sexual behaviour, but increases health awareness and responsibility (Rand et al., 2024).

The approach proposed by the HPVoice project, conducted in Tuscany in 2023–2024, starts from this very awareness. The study showed that the use of digital content co-created with adolescents and tailored to counter specific cognitive *biases* (e.g. emphasising time urgency to counter *present bias*, or empathy and care to counter *omission bias*) can improve the effectiveness of pro-vaccination messages (Casigliani et al., 2022).

2.4 Digital promotion initiatives

In recent years, digital transformation has provided innovative tools to combat vaccine hesitancy, especially among young people. Digital interventions range from automated reminders (SMS, email, push notifications) to participatory social media campaigns, *gamification* tools and interactive web platforms.

Recent meta-analyses show that personalised reminders via SMS or apps significantly increase vaccination coverage among adolescents, improving the timeliness of booster shots and reducing forgetfulness (Currie et al., 2024; Kitaka et al., 2025). At the same time, mobile applications such as *TeenVac* and *Vaccipack* have shown that combining scientific information, playful elements and personalised monitoring increases adherence (Woodall et al., 2025).

In Italy, the National Vaccine Registry and the Electronic Health Record 2.0 are key infrastructures for the implementation of coordinated digital strategies (Agenzia per l'Italia Digitale, 2023). Several regions, including Lombardy and Lazio, have introduced health apps that allow users to book appointments, receive booster notifications and check their vaccination status in real time (Lombardy Region, 2023).

A crucial aspect concerns participatory social media campaigns, such as the HPVoice project in Tuscany, which tested an innovative communication strategy based on the co-creation of digital messages by the adolescent target audience themselves. The study, a three-arm randomised controlled trial, compared three communication strategies on Instagram and TikTok, showing that *peer-based* communication and co-created content generate higher engagement and a perception of greater credibility than traditional institutional messages (Ortiz et al., 2019).

This approach, centred on active participation, aims not only to convey information but also to rebuild trust between institutions and young people, offering communication models based on shared languages, aesthetics and values. Looking ahead, these digital strategies represent a replicable model for health promotion in other areas, integrating educational, social and behavioural dimensions into public communication.

3. Methodology

HCLs are based on the concept and rules of *the Living Lab*¹ (Leminen *et al.*, 2013), i.e. an innovation environment in which citizens, businesses, universities and public bodies **co-create** innovative solutions and apply them in real-life situations. Each HCL represents an innovation project in which these actors collaborate, co-create and implement initiatives and solutions related to the health and well-being of a given community². The main theoretical reference is the perspective of sustainable human development (Biggeri *et al.* 2023), which recognises the centrality of the individual and the community in transformation processes and is based on five pillars - *productivity, equity, environmental sustainability, participation & empowerment, human security* - while emphasising the role of human *collective agency*, which is expressed through interactions between different social actors and guides transitions towards sustainability.

What is Agency?

In the capability approach, developed by Amartya Sen (1999), a conceptual framework defines development and well-being not in terms of wealth or resources, but in terms of real freedoms. This approach deals with three main concepts:

- **Capability (Real Opportunities and Abilities):** These are the real opportunities/abilities and substantial freedom that a person has to do and be what they have reason to value (e.g. having the opportunity to be healthy, to access quality social and health services, to be educated (in health literacy), to participate in decision-making).
- **Functioning:** These are the states and actions that an individual actually achieves (e.g. being well nourished, participating in a debate).
- **Agency:** This is the ability of individuals to act and bring about change based on their own goals concerning their own well-being and that of others.

The approach emphasises that **participation** (in politics and various decision-making processes) has intrinsic and instrumental value, as it expands human freedoms and individual and collective empowerment. Capabilities are highly dependent on conversion factors that are personal, territorial and contextual (similar to the social determinants of health), making the removal of local barriers crucial for full well-being.

The methodology is divided into three phases:

1. Preliminary *phase*: begins with the identification of needs related to a specific health or wellbeing issue (*conceptualisation*), followed by a context analysis in which key

¹ According to the European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL), *Living Labs* are '[...] user-centred, open innovation ecosystems based on a systematic user co-creation approach, integrating research and innovation processes in real-life communities and settings'. See: <https://enoll.org>

² For further information on HCLs, see Biggeri *et al.* 2025a.

stakeholders and key³ s to be involved in the subsequent phases are identified and data useful for the successful implementation phase (*context analysis and planning*) is collected.

2. *Implementation phase*: consists of the co-creation of a prototype together with the stakeholders identified in the previous phase (*design*).
3. *Evaluation phase*: this involves evaluating the process, the prototype created, as well as the dissemination, possible scalability and maintenance over time of the solutions developed, with particular attention to their sustainability.

The structure of the paragraph follows the three operational phases of the project: preliminary phase, implementation phase and evaluation phase, providing details for each phase on the activities carried out, the actors involved, and the data collection and analysis techniques used. Section 2.1 is dedicated to the design of the study, while sub-sections 2.1, 2.2 and 2.3 present the three phases of the project respectively. Each phase is analysed from both an operational and methodological point of view in order to provide a clear and systematic overview of the participatory process undertaken. A short final section is dedicated to ethical aspects.

What is co-creation?

Co-creation is an approach based on **active collaboration between a plurality of stakeholders** (Vargas et al., 2022), aimed at **the creative resolution of shared problems** (McCaffrey et al., 2025; Messiha et al., 2023). This process develops throughout all stages of the initiative, from the exploration and identification of needs or critical issues to the design, implementation and evaluation of solutions or interventions.

In recent years, co-creation has become increasingly important in the context of strengthening health systems. In its global strategy for integrated health services 2016-2026, the World Health Organisation (WHO) promotes a co-creative process for the development of integrated and people-centred health services through the involvement of governments, service providers and citizens (WHO, 2015). Co-creation therefore plays a central role in this area, as **the challenges faced by contemporary public systems, often characterised by increasing social complexity, require the active involvement of a wide range of social actors in public governance** (Torfing & Ansell, 2021).

What is the difference between co-programming, co-design and co-creation?

Co-programming and co-design (Art. 55, Legislative Decree 11/2017) represent structured and regulated forms of collaboration between the public sector and the third sector or between the public sector and citizens, while co-creation is a more recent and

³ A stakeholder is an individual, group of people or organisation actively involved in an initiative, whose interests are negatively or positively affected by the outcome of the implementation or progress of the initiative, and whose actions or reactions in turn influence the stages or completion of a project or the fate of an organisation. See: <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/stakeholder>

broader concept that takes on a wider, horizontal and participatory dimension involving all stakeholders - users, communities, professionals, institutions and research.

- **Co-planning** refers to the phase in which administrations and other actors jointly identify needs, priorities, methods of intervention and resources.
- **Co-design** concerns the following phase, in which the actors involved define and implement specific projects or interventions on the basis of shared planning.
- **Co-creation** goes even further: it involves the participation of all actors from conception, design, implementation and evaluation, with the aim of generating together.

3.1 Study design

The *HPVoice* project was conceived as a participatory communication and experimental evaluation process divided into three main phases: preliminary, implementation and evaluation, with a different number of actors involved (Table 1). In the exploratory phase, high school students were involved in data collection and reflection on their levels of knowledge, perception and attitude towards HPV vaccination, providing insights into the most effective digital channels and languages for reaching their peers. The implementation phase then translated this evidence into a co-creation workshop, the *Social Challenge*, in which other groups of students developed and produced digital content for social media campaigns, experimenting with a health communication approach based on *gamification*, *peer education* and visual creativity. Finally, the evaluation phase tested the effectiveness of communication strategies through a three-arm randomised controlled *trial*, comparing an informative Instagram page, a *de-biasing* page (i.e., one designed to counteract biases that influence decisions) and a control group. Measurements taken over time made it possible to assess the impact of the different strategies on knowledge, vaccine hesitancy, information avoidance and behavioural intentions, highlighting the importance of combining digital interventions and face-to-face training for more effective and informed health communication.

HCL phase	Prototype creation activities	Actors involved			
		Public actors	Private actors	Research institutions	Civil society
Preliminary phase	Conception		x	x	
	Context analysis and planning	x	x	x	
Implementation phase	Design	x	x	x	x
Evaluation phase	Distribution/ Dissemination	x		x	
	Evaluation	x		x	x
	Maintenance	x			

Table 1 - Stakeholders involved in the HCL phases (elaborated from Laurisz et al. 2023).

3.2 Preliminary phase

The exploratory phase of the HPVoice project represented the initial moment of analysis and understanding of the youth context with regard to the issue of HPV prevention and vaccination. Carried out in collaboration with students from classes IV A and B of the Liceo Artistico di Volterra (Art School of Volterra), this phase aimed to assess the level of knowledge, perceptions and information habits of the target population, laying the foundations for the development of subsequent co-creative content. The activity was divided into three main stages: the completion of a questionnaire consisting of 29 items relating to HPV and vaccination; a short training session conducted by the research group and teachers, aimed at filling the main information gaps that emerged; and finally, a participatory consultation to investigate the most effective digital channels and communication methods for reaching peers. During this last activity, participants came up with content proposals for promoting vaccination, using paper templates inspired by the most popular social networks (Instagram, TikTok, Facebook). The results showed uneven knowledge of HPV-related issues — particularly the risks of transmission, gender differences and the need for screening even after vaccination — and a clear preference for Instagram as the main platform for spreading messages. The data collected was then systematised by the researchers to create informative 'pills', divided into three thematic areas ('What is HPV?', 'What is vaccination for?', 'What are the gender differences?'), which formed the scientific basis for the subsequent phases of co-creation of digital content.

3.3 Implementation phase

The implementation phase was the central part of the HPVoice project's co-creative process. It was carried out with classes V A, B and E of the Cavour - Pacinotti Institute in Florence and aimed to transform the results of the exploratory phase into digital communication content capable of promoting HPV vaccination among peers. The activity was organised in

the form of a *Social Challenge*, a participatory methodology that combines elements of training, creativity and gamification. The workshop was divided into three main parts: the completion of a questionnaire to analyse the attitudes and psychological factors that influence the decision to vaccinate; a training session, led by researchers and communication professionals, on the principles of social communication and the most frequent cognitive distortions in prevention behaviours; and finally, the creative workshop itself, in which the students, divided into small groups, created posts and carousels for social networks, mainly Instagram.

During the *Social Challenge*, participants used the scientific 'pills' developed in the previous phase to construct accurate and engaging informational messages, learning to balance rational and emotional content. The work produced drew on three main communication strategies: irony and the use of memes to capture attention, an emotional appeal linked to protecting oneself and others, and intellectual curiosity through quizzes and epidemiological data. The most popular format was the carousel, which allowed for short stories to be told and graphic and textual elements to be integrated.

In summary, the implementation phase allowed us to experiment with an innovative approach to health education, based on the active participation of young people and the use of social media language, with the aim of creating truly effective messages to promote HPV vaccination among adolescents.

3.3.1 The Social Challenge methodology

The *Social Challenge* methodology is a participatory and co-creative approach that uses elements of *gamification* to encourage the active involvement of participants in the implementation of projects or campaigns of social interest. It is based on the idea of learning through challenge and collaboration: participants, organised into groups, tackle a concrete task or real problem, developing creative and shared proposals that are then evaluated on the basis of their effectiveness and originality. The competitive aspect, integrated into a context of cooperation, stimulates motivation, responsibility and personal commitment, while strengthening communication and interpersonal skills.

In education, the *Social Challenge* is an active-participatory methodology that promotes experiential learning and the development of transversal skills, such as critical thinking, teamwork and creativity. In communication and social contexts, on the other hand, it is used to encourage the co-creation of awareness-raising messages or public campaigns, making use of the languages and digital channels of the younger generations. The approach integrates game dynamics, cooperation and empowerment, transforming participants from passive recipients of information to active protagonists in the communication process. In this way, the *Social Challenge* helps to develop awareness, autonomy and a sense of belonging, promoting authentic dialogue between institutions, communities and citizens.

3.4 Evaluation phase

The evaluation phase consists of both an assessment of the co-creation process of the social media pages, through a questionnaire, and the actual experimental phase using the Randomised Controlled Trial (RCT) methodology.

3.4.1 Evaluation questionnaire

During the workshops, participants were given two online questionnaires to complete at the beginning and end of the meetings (Questionnaire of Participation). The questionnaire aims to detect changes in participants' perception of *agency* and to assess their level of satisfaction with the experience. Each response was recorded using an anonymous code. The three areas assessed concern the following areas:

- Perception of factors influencing vaccination behaviour;
- Assessment of participants' agency;
- Satisfaction with participation.

Responses were coded using 5-point Likert scales. The concept of *agency* refers to an individual's ability to act deliberately to pursue personal or collective goals that they value. In particular, people and communities are not passive subjects in their context, but express *agency*, i.e. the ability to act deliberately to pursue goals that they have reason to value and to organise themselves in response to the challenges posed by the environment in which they live (Biggeri and Ferrannini, 2014). In other words, a person is an *agent* (agency) when they are able to make autonomous decisions and actively influence their own life and the surrounding reality, based on their own values, preferences and goals (Crocker & Robeyns, 2009).

3.4.2 Experimental Evaluation

The evaluation phase of the HPVoice project aimed to measure the effectiveness of the communication strategies developed in the previous phases in influencing adolescents' knowledge, attitudes and behaviours with regard to HPV vaccination. To this end, a three-arm *Randomised Controlled Trial* (RCT) was conducted in 22 high school classes in Tuscany, involving a total of 526 students. The classes were randomly assigned to three conditions: a control group, exposed to generic information content from the Istituto Superiore di Sanità (Italian National Institute of Health), and two experimental groups, one exposed to scientific data-based information and the other to messages designed to counter specific cognitive biases related to vaccine hesitancy. The content disseminated via Instagram was co-created with students and health professionals during the implementation phase to ensure its relevance, accuracy and communicative appeal.

3.4.3 The RCT methodology

The *Randomised Controlled Trial* (RCT) methodology is the gold standard for evaluating the effectiveness of an intervention, as it allows causal relationships between action and outcome to be established. It is based on **the randomisation of participants** into two or more groups — an experimental group, which receives the intervention, and one or more control groups, which do not receive it or receive a different version of it. This procedure reduces selection bias and ensures comparability between groups. The RCT involves collecting data before (*pre-test*) and after (*post-test*) the intervention, allowing significant changes in the variables of interest to be measured. In the context of the *HPVoice* project, the single-blind RCT design (i.e. where students did not know which communication group they belonged to) made it possible to compare the effects of different communication strategies — information page, *de-biasing* page and control group — on the level of

knowledge, attitudes and vaccine hesitancy, thus providing an empirical assessment of the impact of health communication actions.

3.5 Ethical Protocol

All participants received oral and written information about the study, its objective, the research design and privacy, with the opportunity to ask questions and withdraw from the study at any time. Written informed consent was obtained prior to their inclusion in the study. The RCT protocol was approved by Pediatric Ethical Committee of Meyer Hospital (<https://www.meyer.it/index.php/ospedale/comitato-etico-pediatrico>).

3.5.1 Privacy and Ethics Committee Approval Procedures

All participants received oral and written information about the study, its objective, research design and privacy, with the opportunity to ask questions and withdraw from the study at any time. Written informed consent was obtained prior to their inclusion in the study.

4. Health Community Lab results

This section summarises the results of the three phases of the HCL methodology. Each phase produced results that were useful for the development of the next phase, culminating in the creation of a prototype of communication content that was implemented for the pilot testing of a promotional campaign in Tuscany.

4.1 Preliminary Analysis Results

The first step involved administering a structured questionnaire consisting of 29 items, aimed at collecting data on basic knowledge of HPV, modes of transmission, related diseases and individual risk perception. The results of the questionnaire revealed uneven and, in some cases, superficial knowledge of the subject: most students recognised the existence of the virus and its connection with certain diseases, but only a minority were aware of the direct link between HPV and cancer, particularly cervical cancer. Many participants were uncertain about the possibility that males could also be infected or transmit the virus, indicating a persistence of gender stereotypes in risk perception.

With regard to vaccination, the data showed a good level of general acceptance, but also a lack of knowledge about how and when it is administered, as well as the fact that the vaccine is recommended for both sexes and is free for adolescents (Figure 1). Some students expressed doubts about the effectiveness and duration of vaccine protection, reflecting a lack of clear and accessible information on the subject.

Figure 2 - Results of the questionnaire on knowledge about HPV and HPV vaccination.

After the quantitative survey phase, an interactive training session was held, led by the project researchers together with the teachers, aimed at filling the main information gaps that had emerged and stimulating critical reflection on the importance of prevention. The activity

was followed by a communicative co-design workshop, in which students developed creative proposals for promoting HPV vaccination, using paper models inspired by the most familiar social media platforms — in particular Instagram, TikTok and Facebook (Figure 3).

The ideas that emerged provided a better understanding of how young people perceive and construct health messages. In general, participants showed a strong preference for visual, concise and ironic language that attracts the attention of their peers and generates identification. Instagram was recognised as the most effective channel for reaching peers, while TikTok was considered useful for short emotional or ironic content. Three **main thematic areas** emerged from the materials produced, which guided the subsequent construction of *the scientific capsules*: (1) *What is HPV?*, (2) *Why is it important to get vaccinated?*, and (3) *Why do males also need to get vaccinated?*

Overall, the preliminary phase provided essential information to guide the design of the digital campaign, highlighting both the information gaps among young people and their ability to actively contribute to the creation of effective communication messages. It also confirmed the value of directly involving students as *co-designers* of public health interventions, with a view to *peer education* and the promotion of health citizenship.

Figure 3 - Mock-ups and drafts of social media content designed by participants in the preliminary phase

4.2 Implementation phase results

The implementation phase saw the use of the information acquired in previous meetings to create the 'scientific pills' that would be used in co-creation with subsequent upper secondary school classes. During the actual co-creation meetings, additional data was collected from participants on the factors considered to have the greatest influence on adolescents' vaccination choices. A central part of this phase is the creation of the prototype social media pages using the Social Challenge methodology. The evaluation framework for this phase also requires all participants and collaborators in the co-creation phase to complete a questionnaire to highlight their level of involvement and satisfaction.

4.2.1 HPVoice science capsules

The *scientific pills* are short pieces of information designed to disseminate basic knowledge about HPV and its prevention in a simple and reliable way. Each pill answers a key question that emerged during the exploratory phase and provides essential information based on scientific evidence, using language suitable for digital channels and peer communication. Their development can be considered a result of the analysis of the weaknesses shown by the students, to which the experts have tried to respond concisely in order to provide support material in the subsequent phases of the HCL. The pills are described below as presented to the students:

What is Papilloma Virus or HPV?

HPV, or human papillomavirus, is a group of over 200 very common types of viruses, transmitted mainly through sexual contact. Most people come into contact with HPV at least once in their lifetime. In most cases, the infection resolves spontaneously, but some strains of the virus — known as high-risk strains — can cause lesions that, over time, can develop into tumours. HPV is responsible for almost all cervical cancers and may also be involved in cancers of the vagina, vulva, penis, anus and oropharynx.

Why is it important to get vaccinated against HPV?

HPV vaccination is a safe and effective method of preventing high-risk virus infections and related cancers. The vaccine stimulates the immune system to produce antibodies that protect against infection, even before exposure to the virus. It is recommended for both girls and boys, preferably between the ages of 11 and 12, i.e. before the onset of sexual activity. In Italy, vaccination is free for adolescents in the age group covered by the vaccination schedule and is one of the most effective tools for cancer prevention.

Why is it important for boys to be vaccinated too?

HPV does not only affect women: males can also contract and transmit the virus, developing infections and lesions that can lead to anal, penile or oral cancers. Getting vaccinated therefore means protecting oneself and contributing to the protection of the community by reducing the circulation of the virus in the population. In addition, male vaccination promotes greater gender equity in prevention and strengthens the overall effectiveness of public health strategies against HPV.

4.2.2 Outcome of the Social Challenge

During the *Social Challenge*, participants used the scientific 'pills' developed in the previous phase to construct accurate and engaging informational messages, learning to balance rational and emotional content. The work produced leveraged three main communication strategies: irony and the use of memes to capture attention, an emotional appeal linked to protecting oneself and others, and cognitive curiosity through quizzes and epidemiological data. The most popular format was the carousel, which allowed for short stories to be told and graphic and textual elements to be integrated (Figure 4).

The evaluation conducted by the experts awarded the carousel 'A match against the Papilloma Virus', which reinterpreted prevention as a sporting challenge between 'teams', making the message accessible and motivating. The content that emerged from this phase was then reworked by the research group to enhance its clarity, communicative effectiveness

and consistency with the principles of *de-biasing*, in particular by balancing the use of *framing* and promoting a gain-oriented perspective (*gain frame*).

Figure 4. Images of posts and carousels co-created by participants during the implementation phase.

4.3 Evaluation phase results

The graph shows the highest and lowest average scores emerging from the analysis of the variables measured during the implementation phase of the *HPVoice* project. The values are expressed on a Likert scale from 1 to 4 and illustrate the factors perceived as more or less important by the students involved (Figure 5).

Among the aspects with the highest scores are knowledge about HPV and concern about the consequences of infection, which show a relatively good basic awareness and widespread recognition of the relevance of the issue to one's health. High scores also emerge for the perception of the usefulness of knowing about healthcare facilities and services dedicated to prevention, a sign of a concrete interest in accessing information and professional support. These results indicate that, despite gaps in knowledge, adolescents show a generally positive and attentive attitude towards sexual and reproductive health.

Conversely, the lowest scores mainly concern relational and psychological barriers to discussing the issue with adults or health professionals, such as fear of judgement, discomfort in talking about sexuality, or lack of knowledge about how to access services. These results suggest that, although students recognise the importance of the topic, there are still obstacles related to communication and access to information, which may limit the effectiveness of prevention messages.

Overall, the graph confirms that the exploratory phase highlighted a good level of awareness of the risks associated with HPV, but also the need to strengthen information and relational skills by creating safe and accessible spaces for communication. This evidence guided the design of the next phase, orienting communication strategies towards a more direct, peer-oriented language capable of overcoming emotional and social barriers.

Figure 5. Results of the questionnaire on behavioural and social impact factors in vaccination behaviour

It can be seen that the perception of agency shows a slight increase from pre (4.30) to post (4.51). This suggests that the workshop, based on participatory and creative methodologies, helped to strengthen participants' perception of control and protagonism in the learning and communication process (Figure 6).

Overall satisfaction reached an average score of 4.16, indicating a highly positive evaluation of the training experience. This result reflects the good level of engagement generated by the workshop format, based on co-creation and the use of expressive languages familiar to young people, such as social media and visual practices.

Figure 6 - Results of the questionnaire on agency and satisfaction of participants in the implementation phase

Overall, the data suggest that the *HPVoice* workshop not only generated high satisfaction among participants, but also promoted a strengthening of the sense of personal and participatory competence, a central objective of HCL on which the project is based.

4.3.1 Evaluation in the experimental phase: evaluation of the prototype

HCL is also evaluated using the results of the co-creative phase in the subsequent experimental phase. The Instagram page templates were implemented in two real accounts on the social platform and used to test their effectiveness within an RCT procedure.

The final prototype integrated the social content created by peers in the previous phases through the creation of two social pages on Instagram dedicated to the *HPVoice* project. The pages were created by researchers developing posts and 'carousels' for the next experimental phase of the project.

The two pages use two different communication approaches to test the effectiveness of social communication towards adolescents.

The (red) page called '*HPVoice*' uses a communication method based on de-biasing, i.e. persuasive communication that aims to counteract the cognitive distortions outlined in the introduction: information avoidance, present bias and the framing effect.

The (blue) page called '*Progetto HPV*' uses an approach that is more focused on communicating information and describing concepts related to vaccination and HPV.

Figure 7 - Instagram pages implemented for the experimental phase (de-biasing page on the left, information page on the right).

The evaluation was conducted through three surveys (T1, T2, T3) distributed over three months in 22 classes in Tuscany (provinces of Pisa, Grosseto and Lucca), aimed at measuring knowledge of HPV, the level of *vaccine hesitancy*, the tendency to avoid information and the intention to use sexual and reproductive health services (Figure 8). The results showed that, overall, social media campaigns had a limited effect on reducing vaccine hesitancy, but highlighted an important moderating role of *information avoidance*: in subjects less inclined to avoid health information, informative communication significantly reduced *vaccine hesitancy*, while in subjects with a high tendency to avoid information, the effect was the opposite. Furthermore, a subsequent face-to-face intervention led to a significant increase in knowledge about HPV, highlighting the effectiveness of combining digital tools and direct training.

In summary, the evaluation phase allowed for the experimental validation of the co-creative approach of the HPVoice project, while identifying the limitations and potential of social media use for health promotion among young people and providing empirical evidence useful for the development of more personalised communication strategies that are aware of the psychological mechanisms that influence vaccination decisions.

The graph shows the comparison between the three experimental groups of the *HPVoice* project — control group, group exposed to the information page and group exposed to the *de-biasing* page — in relation to the average scores for **vaccine hesitancy** and **knowledge about HPV** measured at time T1 (baseline) and time T2 (after exposure to the Instagram campaign).

Figure 8. Results of the experimental phase before and after the dissemination of the communication intervention on social media. The average scores on the Vaccine Hesitancy (left) and HPV Knowledge (right) scales are shown.

Overall, vaccine hesitancy levels remain largely stable in the control and *de-biasing* groups, while showing a slight reduction in the information group, from an average score of 4.0 to 3.7. This suggests a potentially positive, albeit limited, effect of science-based information content in reducing vaccine hesitancy among participants. However, the change is modest, confirming the findings of the paper's statistical analysis, according to which the overall effect of the campaign was marginal and modulated by individual variables, such as the tendency to avoid information.

With regard to knowledge about HPV, the average scores appear to be substantially unchanged between T1 and T2 in all groups, with a minimal increase (from 2.7 to 2.8) observed in the information group. This suggests that exposure to digital content alone was not sufficient to significantly increase knowledge on the subject, confirming the importance of integrating social communication with face-to-face training sessions, such as those subsequently carried out in the project.

In summary, the graph shows that the information page produced a small improvement in terms of both knowledge and reduction in vaccine hesitancy, while the de-biasing page showed no significant effects. These results confirm the need for multi-level communication strategies that combine scientifically accurate content, accessible language and direct educational interventions to promote greater vaccine awareness among young people.

Figure 9 - Graph showing the effect of the information page (HPV Project) on participants' vaccine hesitancy, based on their level of information avoidance.

4.3.2 The limitations and prospects of the research

The results of the HCL HPV clearly show the usefulness of a co-creation phase with the target population for the development of an appropriate intervention, which is suitable in form and content to promote behavioural change in order to bring innovation to the system/community in which it is implemented. The co-creation phase therefore fits perfectly as a starting point for the development of a solution that can be tested, but also allows for more in-depth work on the target population. It is precisely in this discrepancy between co-creation activities and the application of communication products that it was possible to identify a difference in the impact of activities throughout the HCL. While the prototype design and initial consultation activities with adolescents allowed for their active participation with experimenters and experts, the final solutions relating to the Instagram pages culminated in a more passive communication strategy. The different levels of interactivity with the workshop topic, i.e. vaccination, led to different levels of involvement and agency among participants, favouring those who carried out interactive activities and reworked the concepts they had learned.

The creation of the Instagram pages certainly demonstrated the possibility of implementing HCL solutions in a realistic scenario, with the benefit of authentic language created by young people for their peers, but it also highlighted the channel used for adolescents with a greater tendency to avoid health information.

This result means that, despite the innovation in language and form, barriers remain in relation to the means chosen to communicate the intervention for the promotion of vaccination. Young users of social media channels perceive health promotion activities that exploit these channels as paternalistic interference, almost as if they were a *ploy* by institutions (educational or health) to influence their freedom of choice. This conclusion is all the more true when attributed to the limited impact of the intervention on those with a high level of 'information avoidance', and in particular to the *de-biasing* communication strategy.

5. Conclusions of the Health Community Lab project

The *HCL – HPVoice* project was a significant research-intervention experience in the field of health education, youth participation and educational innovation. Developed according to the *HCL* methodological model, the main objective of the project was to promote health awareness and literacy with regard to the Papilloma Virus (HPV) and vaccination, actively involving students in an experiential and co-creative learning process.

The *HCL* paradigm is based on the idea that health promotion cannot be limited to the vertical transmission of information, but must take the form of a process of collective construction of knowledge and responsibility, in which citizens — and young people in particular — become an integral part of the educational and health community. In this sense, the *HPVoice* project has integrated the principles of *HCL* with the tools of digital communication and participatory design, creating a learning laboratory focused on people, contexts and contemporary languages.

The exploratory phase was the starting point of the process, providing a detailed snapshot of students' knowledge, perceptions and representations of HPV. The results of the questionnaire administered in schools highlighted widespread gaps in information, particularly on the correlation between HPV and cancer, but also a genuine interest in the subject and a willingness to discuss it. This phase also made it possible to identify the most effective communication channels and codes of expression for reaching young people, providing a valuable framework for the subsequent planning of activities.

The implementation phase, developed using the *Social Challenge* methodology, translated the research results into concrete action. The students, organised into working groups, were invited to design and produce digital content for awareness campaigns on HPV and vaccination, using tools and languages specific to the world of social media. This process encouraged active participation, cooperation and critical reflection, allowing participants to move from being passive recipients of health messages to co-creators of scientific communication. The playful and competitive nature of the *Social Challenge* also stimulated creativity, motivation and a sense of belonging, transforming the workshop into a dynamic context of shared learning.

Finally, the evaluation phase made it possible to measure the impact of the experience in terms of knowledge, attitudes and personal skills. The quantitative and qualitative results show a moderate increase in the sense of *agency* — understood as the perception of self-efficacy and the ability to actively influence the social context — and a high level of *satisfaction* with the experience. These results confirm the ability of the *HCL* model to foster individual and collective empowerment, promoting meaningful learning and informed participation in the construction of public health messages.

The *HPVoice* experience has shown that the *HCL* methodology can be an effective response to the contemporary challenge of combining education, communication and participation in the health sector. The project has demonstrated that the direct involvement of young people, the enhancement of their creativity and the use of familiar digital tools make it possible to translate complex scientific concepts into accessible forms of communication, thus promoting lasting cultural change.

From a pedagogical and social point of view, the HCL workshop helped participants develop not only information and digital skills, but also relational, reflective and collaborative skills. The co-creation of content stimulated young people's awareness of their role in promoting health, transforming them from users into active health citizenship actors. Furthermore, the dialogue between students, teachers, healthcare professionals and researchers made it possible to build a true learning community, in which expert and experiential knowledge complement each other.

In conclusion, the *HCL – HPVoice* project has highlighted the transformative potential of an educational approach based on participation, interdisciplinarity and co-creation. The experience suggests that models such as HCL can be effectively replicated in other educational and thematic contexts, promoting not only an increase in knowledge, but also the growth of a sense of responsibility, critical thinking and the ability to actively contribute to the well-being of one's community. At a time when misinformation and the distance between science and citizenship represent crucial challenges, experiences such as *HPVoice* demonstrate that participatory education and inclusive communication are fundamental tools for building informed, competent and supportive communities.

5.1 Policy recommendations and prospects for the Tuscany Region

The results of the *HCL – HPVoice* project offer relevant insights for the development of regional policies on health promotion, prevention and youth participation, particularly in the context of the Tuscany Region. The experience has demonstrated the effectiveness of educational and communication models based on active involvement, co-design and digital languages, highlighting how such strategies can strengthen *health literacy* and confidence in prevention pathways. In line with the Regional Prevention Plan (PRP) 2020–2025, which recognises the role of schools as a privileged setting for health promotion, the HCL approach can be a useful operational methodology for integrating health and pedagogical skills into ongoing projects aimed at adolescents.

From the point of view of educational and health policies, experience suggests that it would be beneficial to develop regional programmes that adopt the *HCL* model as a permanent mechanism for collaboration between schools, health services and local communities. The creation of local HCL laboratories could promote the spread of peer education practices, co-creation of scientific content and empathetic communication about health, improving young people's ability to critically interpret information and actively participate in decisions affecting their well-being.

A further valuable element is the possibility of integrating the HCL approach with the actions already promoted by the Tuscan Network of Health Promoting Institutes (Rete SHE) and the Prevention Departments of local health authorities, creating stable synergies between the various actors in the education and health system. The positive results in terms of *agency* and *satisfaction* show that students not only learn better when they are personally involved, but also become multipliers of positive messages in their communities.

Looking ahead, the data emerging from *HPVoice* can therefore guide the Tuscany Region towards more participatory, inclusive and digitally aware prevention policies, capable of combining methodological innovation and social cohesion. Investing in HCL laboratories throughout the region would mean not only promoting health, but also supporting a civic culture of shared responsibility, strengthening the link between institutions, citizens and the region.

The Future of HCL

HCLs were created to activate shared and sustainable innovation processes, in which the community and stakeholders become protagonists. Their purpose is not to co-create temporary solutions, but to leave the responsibility and capacity to carry them forward over time in the hands of the community. Each HCL therefore aims to build autonomy and collective *agency*, encouraging the creation of local networks capable of sustaining and regenerating the change produced.

To ensure that these local experiences do not remain isolated initiatives but become structural policies and stable tools for innovation in the regional healthcare system, a further step is necessary: the creation of *the Health Community Hub* (HC HUB).

The HC HUB represents the evolutionary perspective of HCLs: a regional platform for coordination, learning and enhancement, capable of ensuring methodological consistency, disseminating and replicating innovations, and integrating results into healthcare system policies and services. Without such an institutional and political framework, HCLs would risk remaining episodic experiments, whereas their potential is to become permanent drivers of systemic innovation, serving the health and well-being of Tuscan communities.

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